

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF IMPLEMENTING INTEGRATED INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT COMPETENCE IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. A higher educational institution should teach students throughout the years, while improving their knowledge, they should be trained in various types of activities, and should be encouraged to achieve their desires. However, the higher education system implemented in our country today has a very broad goal.

Keywords: development, innovations, credit- module, competence, system, student, integration, technology, subjects, improving, knowledge

The process of using innovative technologies in higher education institutions is evident both in the content of subjects and in the methods, tools and forms of teaching. [1; 614-620 -pp]. Nowadays, world education has great challenges. The main requirement is to raise the quality of moral-ethical and intellectual development of the young generation to the next level, to teach them to adapt to the rapidly changing world. At the same time, it is aimed at introducing innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process (Fig. 1).

1.- picture. Development of student competence in the higher education system using innovative technologies and educational programs

The scheme presented below provides an algorithm for developing student competence in interdisciplinary education using innovative technologies and educational programs. [2; 2419-2423-pp.].

Control of the formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications and general competences has an important place in the educational process. In particular, control functions may entail a number of tasks and requirements. Controlling and evaluating students' knowledge means to be creative, independent thinking, to constantly improve their knowledge, and to use literature widely. At the same time, it strengthens the connection between the teacher and the student, and it strengthens the two interrelated means of teaching. In this, the professors-teachers' pay attention to the lectures and practical trainings, responsible cooperation and tireless work in creating evaluation standards and criteria, questionnaires, test questions and various puzzles and related concepts.

The processes of integration that took place in Europe at the end of the 20th century led to the need to use a single credit-module system in higher education institutions, and in 1999, in Europe, called the Bologna process, mutual cooperation between the ministries of higher education

of the European countries was established. The international development forum has started work. In Uzbekistan, the first steps towards the transition to the credit-module system were initiated by the European Union TESIS (Organizational Assistance to the Commonwealth of Independent States) technical assistance program for the Commonwealth of Independent States and the Asian Development Bank's reform of education in Uzbekistan. 2000-2008 studies were carried out through the plan. Starting from the 2020-2021 academic year, the procedure for transferring the educational process to the step-by-step credit-module system was implemented in higher education institutions of the Republic. According to the "Consercioua for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the decree of the Resident of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2019, it is planned that 85 percent of HEIs in the country will switch to the step-by-step credit-module system by 2030. According to him, each subject taught at the university is now reflected in credits depending on the amount of tuition. For example, each subject can average 5, 6 or 7.5 credits. A student can earn a certain amount of credits in each semester, and depending on this amount, he will be awarded a bachelor's or master's degree. [3; 48-51-pp., 4; 248-251-pp., 5; 68-71-pp.].

ESTS - Euro Credit Transfer System, originally founded in 1989, is a credit distribution system developed, tested and improved by Euro countries. The ESTS system is a system that provides for the free transfer of the student's knowledge from one country (HEI) to another country (HEI), free recognition of acquired skills and qualifications, and a degree taking into account everything.

In the ESTS system, all types of education (day, evening, part-time, distance learning) and all forms of teaching (lecture, practice, laboratory, etc.) can be used. [6; 262-265-pp., 7; 105-107-pp].

In the credit-module system, 1 credit is equivalent to an average of 25-30 academic hours of study. It is necessary for a student to master a certain amount of study material in order to accumulate the appropriate credits in a given subject. The study program is 40-50% classroom hours, 50-60% independent work hours in the bachelor's degree, 30%-40% classroom hours, 60-70% independent work hours (except for master's practical and graduation work) split. The amount of credit hours and tuition is determined by the board of the higher education institution and must be transparently posted on the higher education institution's website.

The model for improving the theoretical and practical foundations of the use of innovative technologies in higher education institutions: consists of motivational-targeted, methodological approaches, technological processes and diagnostic components. [8; 84-88-pp., 9; 413-417-pp.].

The model for improving the theoretical and practical foundations of the use of innovative technologies in the credit-module system in higher education institutions: consists of motivational-targeted, methodological adaptations, technological processes and diagnostic components. The credit-module system is a process of organizing education and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies and a credit ratio. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process.

In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturity of the student. It is aimed at ensuring the knowledge of the scholar throughout his life and forming human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements.

Picture 2. Basic functions of the credit module system

Two basic issues are emphasized in the principle of the credit module: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of students' knowledge based on reuting. The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit module system (Fig. 2). The above should not only conduct the training based on innovative educational technologies, but also study and learn independently from the student, have a positive attitude towards education, acquire the necessary and deep theoretical knowledge based on the demand of the labor market. , consists of teaching to form practical skills.

According to foreign experience, in the credit-module system, the educational process consists of 2-4 additional modules per semester. The subjects included in the module are formed from easy to complex, from theoretical-methodical subjects to practical subjects and based on the principle of logical complementarity. In order for a student to become a specialist, it is necessary to acquire not only information, but also the ability to process and implement it. Module-based training programs are developed based on a special scheme and include the following:

Educational goals and tasks are completely exceeded;

Requirements for the student's qualifications, which must be acquired after starting and finishing the subject (course);

Short version of teaching: methods and means of teaching; consists of methods and forms of knowledge assessment.

A brief content (syllabus) of each subject included in the module, i.e. topics of lectures, a plan of seminars and practical trainings, tasks designed to evaluate independent education;

The editorial capacity of the credit-module system of educational organization includes the following as a set of its possibilities (social-cultural, systematic, organizational, legal and conditional): availability of information and content resources;

Pay attention to identifying and eliminating the difficulties of students and teachers in the activity of self-education;

Cooperative interaction between teacher and student, freedom to choose organizational forms, methods, and means of self-education activity, the possibility of choosing the individual-personal trajectory of the student's self-education activity;

It involves the training of students' skills for various forms of independent educational activity. The editorial structure of the credit-module system of training organization reflects the process of skill formation in their entirety. At the same time, the starting point is to understand the credit (Credit, Credit-hour) as a single unit for measuring the volume of the student's/teacher's academic work. One credit is equal to 1 academic hour of the student's weekly classroom work during the academic period. 2 hours (100 minutes) of independent study are conducted for each academic hour of lecture, practice (seminar) and seminar classes. In the information age, in the history of mankind, there have been great achievements in the world of industry and science. Information has become the most valuable thing in the world. The invention of the computer led to the simplification of human tasks. Modern teaching and learning tools were introduced in the fields of science and education. Now, the importance of electronic methods and manuals in this field is increasing. Initially, electronic manuals were in the form of simple text, but now they include various images. In today's society, the use of information technologies is becoming a practical necessity in all areas of human activity. Forming the skills of using these technologies in most cases ensures the success of today's student's career. We know that when a person sees information, he remembers it more than when he simply hears or reads it. Taking into account these aspects, electronic method and manual transmission can lead to a long period of use. The development of various animation programs has led to the development of high-quality electronic methods and manuals in the field of electronic methods and manuals. Now, the importance of electronic methods and manuals in this field is increasing. Initially, electronic manuals were in the form of simple text, but now they include various images. The possibility of using Flash, 3D Max and other types of animations, various video and audio fouds in electronic methods and manuals has become available in the program of electronic methods and manuals. The most convenient use of these possibilities depends on the skills and psychological compatibility of the user of electronic methods and manuals. Currently, Internet technologies are also developing rapidly. There are special tutors and audios for online education. Distance learning technologies are being introduced. This brings a lot of benefits to students.

In this case, students can study in universities of another country and get a diploma from that university [10; 554-558-pp., 11; 146-150-pp.]. Using modern technologies in the educational process to increase the efficiency of the lesson is an urgent issue that is necessary in the teaching of subjects. Interest in the use of editorial, information and innovative technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. [12; 252-255-pp]. The future of every society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part of it and a necessary necessity. Today, reforming and improving the continuous education system of our country, which is moving from the beginning of independent development, raising it to the level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies to it, and increasing the effectiveness of education has been raised to the level of state policy. At the same time, in traditional education, students are taught to acquire only theoretical knowledge, but in modern technology, students are taught to independently search, analyze, and draw conclusions about the knowledge they need to acquire. [13; 10-44-pp., 14; 110-120-pp].

3.- picture. Innovative conduct of training in the credit-module system

The basis of innovative educational technologies depends on the selected technologies, so that the teacher and students can achieve the specified result in cooperation. In teaching, the main attention is focused on learning the basic factors, concepts, laws, theories and methods of astronomy, students' independent application of their knowledge in explaining astronomical phenomena, experimental results, and the operation of equipment. Students' acquisition of subject knowledge and skills is assessed through oral question-and-answer, laboratory work, and explanation of events, experiences, concepts, and laws. [15; 96-99- pp]. The innovativeness of compulsory subjects (as an example of the Astronomy course) is conditioned by the following (Figure 3)

Conclusion: When teaching with modern technologies, the student thinks independently, especially when studying with the help of computer technologies, the student quickly acquires various knowledge and skills. Lessons conducted with such technologies teach students to think independently, develop their speech, communicate with each other, and even make their own conclusions. Since the introduction of innovations into education has a dialectical description, it is effective in all respects to use innovative technologies that serve to successfully solve the tasks of learning, implementing, assimilating and implementing innovations.

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